

Dendrochronological analysis of additional timber from the ships ‘Bispevika 12’, Oslo.

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Dendro.dk report 46 : 2020

Commissioned by Sarah Fawsitt, Norsk Maritimt Museum.

Four samples from ship Bispevika 12a, found during excavations in Oslo, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis. Samples from five samples that were thought initially to be from the same ship were analysed previously (Daly & Daly 2016a). When the material was excavated and documented the remains have been categorised as three separate ships, Bi12a, Bi12b and Bi12c (Sarah Fawsitt pers comm). In this report the results of the analysis of the samples from all three ships that have been analysed dendrochronologically are presented.

The samples from Bi12a are from four planks and a keel. Ship Bi12b is represented by two samples, both from planks. Ship Bi12c is similarly represented by two plank samples. All the material is *Quercus sp.*, oak. All samples are dated.

Fig. 1. Bispevika 12, Oslo. Diagram showing the chronological position of the tree-ring curves from the timbers from the three boats.

Bispevika 12a

Plank x175 (Z157101a)

Plank x175 contains 132 tree-rings, and outermost, the heartwood/sapwood boundary is observed. This plank is tangentially converted from the parent tree. The tree-ring curve from this plank covers the period AD 1412-1543. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree used to make the plank is estimated to c. AD 1553-68 (fig. 1).

Plank x157 (Z157104a)

Plank x157 is tangentially converted from the parent tree. It contains 158 tree-rings of which 11 are sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve from this plank covers the period AD 1405-1562. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree used to make this plank is estimated to c. AD 1563-76 (fig. 1).

Plank x213 (Z157102a) and plank x186 (Z157103a)

Plank x213 is tangentially converted from the parent tree. It contains 116 tree-rings of which 15 are sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve from this plank covers the period AD 1452-1567. Plank x186 contains 106 tree-rings all heartwood and covers the period AD 1441-1546. The correlation between these two planks is so high ($t = 14.48$) leading to the suggestion that these two are made from the same tree. Allowing for missing sapwood, the tree that these two planks were made from was felled c. AD 1568-77 (see fig. 1).

				Z157101a	Z157104a	Z157001a	Z157103a	Z157102a	Z157002a	Z1570039	Z1570059	Z157004a
Bi12a Average Z157M003	Same tree	x175	Z157101a	*	6.59	5.14	5.95	4.97	0.37	2.96	0.12	2.7
		x157	Z157104a	6.59	*	6.28	8.62	5.99	2.86	5.6	3.79	1.53
		X192	Z157001a	5.14	6.28	*	10.28	8.94	3.31	6.71	0.71	4.52
		x186	Z157103a	5.95	8.62	10.28	*	14.48	2.55	5.22	2.94	4.31
		x213	Z157102a	4.97	5.99	8.94	14.48	*	2.12	5.92	3.22	3.01
Bi12c Ave Z157 M004		x024	Z157002a	0.37	2.86	3.31	2.55	2.12	*	6.49	3.58	2.79
		x032	Z1570039	2.96	5.6	6.71	5.22	5.92	6.49	*	5.24	5.93
Bi12b Ave Z157 M005		x063	Z1570059	0.12	3.79	0.71	2.94	3.22	3.58	5.24	*	5.63
		x048	Z157004a	2.7	1.53	4.52	4.31	3.01	2.79	5.93	5.63	*

Table 1. Bispevika Bi12, Oslo. The correlation between all the dated samples from the three ships.

Keel timber X192 (Z175001a)

Keel x192 contains 175 tree-rings, all heartwood rings. The tree-ring curve from the keel covers the period AD 1365-1539. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree used to make this keel is estimated to be after AD 1550 (fig. 1).

If it is assumed that the timbers for the building of ship Bi12a took place on one occasion, then we might consider a combination of the felling estimates for all dated samples and suggest that the trees for these were felled in the period c. AD 1568 or some few years later (marked with orange in fig. 1).

Bispevika 12b

Just two planks are analysed dendrochronologically, so far, from ship Bispevika 12b. The dating of these is reported previously (Daly & Daly 2016a) but now we can separate these from the samples from the other Bi12 ships. Both these planks are tangentially converted from the parent tree.

Plank x048 (Z157004a) contains 142 tree-rings, all heartwood. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1404-1545. The felling date for the tree used to make this plank is estimated to be after c. AD 1553 (fig. 1).

Filenames	-	-	Z157M003 Bi12a	
-	start	dates	AD1365	
-	dates	end	AD1567	
Master chronologies				
WSwedM25	AD1344	AD1560	13.81	West Sweden 49 timbers (Daly unpubl)
SE08M003	AD1348	AD1634	13.19	Uddevalla 191 1 SU Trappan 6 timbers (Daly 2018b)
SScanM25	AD1343	AD1548	12.44	Southern Scandinavia 36 timbers (Daly unpubl)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	10.54	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	9.61	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
D0137M04	AD1286	AD1520	9.59	TBT Odense group4 12 timbers (Daly & Daly 2019)
D014M001	AD1319	AD1521	8.78	Nørregade Gråbrødrekløsters baghave 2 timbers (Daly 2015a)
2121M002	AD1052	AD1596	8.77	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001b)
SM100001	AD1310	AD1539	7.90	Ystad area (Lund University)
2M000005	AD1316	AD1514	7.88	Sjælland kirker (e.g. Daly 1998a&b)
B012M001	AD1347	AD1484	7.82	Copenhagen Admiralgade 3 timbers (Daly 2005)
8113M001	AD1350	AD1440	7.66	Mårup K. 9 timbers (Daly 1998d)
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	7.16	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
2117M001	AD1316	AD1514	7.10	Hammer K. 5 trees (Daly 1998a)
Chronologies from Scandinavian exports				
EP31539	AD1361	AD1539	13.47	Stirling Castle Scotland (Crone pers comm)
B027oak C	AD1331	AD1557	13.34	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 23 timbers (Daly 2016f)
EP41592	AD1390	AD1592	11.93	Stirling Castle Scotland episode 4 (Crone pers comm)
q415029m04	AD1356	AD1540	11.53	Evangelistas altarpiece Seville Cathedral 29 planks (Rodríguez-Trobajo & Domínguez-Delmás 2015)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	11.07	Ålborg Østerå & Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)
NB700000	AD1345	AD1538	10.83	Helsingør (Nationalmuseet)
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	10.73	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group 24 timber (Daly 1998e)
2090M001	AD1349	AD1549	10.18	Højbro Plads Brønd AIT (Eriksen 1995)
4077M00Z	AD1310	AD1546	9.65	Nyborg Slot Renaissance phase 38 timbers (Daly 2007)
B028M003	AD1386	AD1576	8.25	Køge Havn 4 timbers (Daly 2013d)
B037M001	AD1337	AD1550	8.25	Favrholm Mølle 20 timbers (Daly 2016g)
H012M001	AD1379	AD1576	8.19	Sankelmarksgade Aalborg sogn 4 timbers (Daly 2016c)
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	8.17	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
8111M002	AD1350	AD1480	8.09	Astrup K. 7 timbers (Daly 1998c)
H009M001	AD1410	AD1613	8.02	Strandgade Nibe bolværk A6 3 timbers (Daly 2016a)
B027oak B p...	AD1248	AD1532	7.97	Gammel Strand Copenhagen B purple 21 timbers (Daly 2016f)
B027oak E pink	AD1315	AD1663	7.62	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak pink 5 timbers (Daly 2016f)
H011M001	AD1386	AD1563	7.45	Aalborg Algade Tiendeladen hus 4 timbers (Daly 2016b)
F2RW	AD1362	AD1476	7.43	St Serfs church Dysart (Crone pers comm)
Chronologies from ships				
Z073m001	AD1385	AD1574	12.44	Barcode 14 ship Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2011d)
Z141M001	AD1352	AD1539	10.32	Klippan 2 shipwreck Göteborg 11 timbers (Daly 2015b)
Z040M001	AD1386	AD1567	10.08	Gåsehage Randers 2 timbers (Daly 2009)
Z089m001	AD1399	AD1581	9.79	Oslo Barcode skib 5. 9 timbers (Daly 2013a)
Z0923M03	AD1328	AD1618	9.19	Vasa group 3 31 timbers (Daly in press)
Z249M001	AD1375	AD1588	9.19	Bispevika 16 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019b)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	9.03	B&W Grund Vrag 2. 2 trees (Daly 1997; 2000b)
Z064M001	AD1313	AD1481	8.94	Oslo Sørenga 9 3 timbers (Daly 2011b)
Z147M002	AD1363	AD1535	8.59	Bispevika 4 ship Oslo B3B7 5 timbers (Daly 2016d)
Z280M001	AD1362	AD1564	7.38	Femern vestlig landvinding VIR2929 3 timbers (Daly 2020b)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	7.09	Klim Strandvraget 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)

Table 2. Bispevika Bi12a, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the average for Bi12a and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Plank x063 (Z1570059) contains 65 tree-rings, of which 15 are sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1501-1565. Allowing for missing sapwood, the estimated felling date for the tree used for this plank can be placed at c. AD 1566-71 (fig. 1). If these two trees were felled at the same time for building Bi12b, then this felling took place c. AD 1566-71 (highlighted with blue in fig. 1).

Bispevika 12c

Just two planks are analysed from ship Bispevika 12c. They are both tangentially converted from the parent tree.

Plank x024 (Z157002a) contains 176 tree-rings, all heartwood, and covers the period AD 1382-1557. Allowing for missing sapwood we can place the felling of the tree for this plank at after ca. AD 1565.

Plank x032 (Z1570039) contains 146 tree-rings, including 10 sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve from this plank covers the period AD 1414-1559. Allowing for missing sapwood we can place the felling of the tree for this plank at ca. AD 1560-70. Combining the results of the dating of these two samples indicates a date for the building of Bispevika 12c at c. AD 1565-70 (highlighted with green in fig. 1).

Filenames	-	-	Z157M004 Bi12c	Z157M005 Bi12b	
-	start	dates	AD1382	AD1404	
-	dates	end	AD1559	AD1565	
Master chronologies					
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	5.28	4.58	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
Chronologies from ships					
Z109001_2_5	AD1437	AD1597	10.09	5.15	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo same tree 1 2 5 (Daly 2013c)
SHIPS_3_norway	AD1304	AD1727	9.77	8.76	BC Larvik portørenga 34 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z253M001	AD1339	AD1566	9.47	8.08	Bispevika 18 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019b)
Z109M001	AD1437	AD1597	9.23	7.08	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013c)
Z0302M04	AD1407	AD1591	8.92	6.03	Oslo Barcode ship BC02 6 timbers (Daly 2014)
Z0307M01	AD1435	AD1585	8.84	4.26	Barcode ship BC07 5 timbers (Daly 2010b)
Z110M001	AD1342	AD1601	8.57	6.20	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013c)
Z160M001	AD1426	AD1525	7.06	-	Bispevika 8 ship Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2016c)
Z065M002	AD1355	AD1617	7.02	-	Bjørsvika Kenneth Oslo 5 timbers (Daly 2011c)
Z086M001	AD1468	AD1584	6.79	6.08	Havnelageret 1 Oslo boat 3 timbers (Daly 2013b)
Z0306M01	AD1418	AD1585	6.69	5.83	Barcode 6 6 timbers (Daly 2010a)
Z283M001	AD1472	AD1598	6.58	5.27	Bispekilenflaket Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2020a)
Z160M003	AD1422	AD1526	5.98	-	Bispevika 8 ship Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2019a)
Z071m004	AD1304	AD1595	5.37	-	Oslo Barcode BC08 5 timbers (Daly 2011d)
Z280M001	AD1362	AD1564	5.22	5.14	Femern vestlig landvinding 3 timbers (Daly 2020b)
Z177M001	AD1434	AD1518	5.21	-	Bispevika 14 ship Oslo 2 timbers (Daly & Daly 2016b)
Chronologies from Scandinavian exports					
H017M001	AD1434	AD1598	6.71	5.75	Aalborg Danmarksgade A3 2 timbers (Daly 2018a)
N0253M01short	AD1420	AD1621	6.40	5.02	Oslo Bispevika B3B7 PINE 61 timbers SHORT (Daly 2016h)
CARNCKx8	AD1317	AD1588	5.85	4.18	Carnock Castle Scotland IMPORTS (Crone pers comm)
B027oak E pink	AD1315	AD1663	5.72	5.56	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak pink 5 timbers (Daly 2016f)
B027oak C	AD1331	AD1557	5.43	5.15	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 23 timbers (Daly 2016f)
CD60IZ01	AD1450	AD1635	5.42	6.06	Ryomgård 9 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	5.38	4.04	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
4077M00Z	AD1310	AD1546	5.32	6.74	Nyborg Slot renaissance phase 38 timbers (Daly 2007)
EDINCAS2	AD1358	AD1509	5.18	4.12	Edinburgh Castle IMPORTS 13 timbers (Crone pers comm)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	4.55	5.42	Ålborg Østerå & Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)

Table 3. Bispevika Bi12b and Bi12c, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the averages of ships Bi12b and Bi12c and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Provenance

The correlation between the tree-ring curves from the samples from all three ships is shown in table 1. The five samples from Bi12a form a clear homogeneous group, and these are averaged to form a mean curve Z157M003, representing four trees, of 203 years in length. The four samples from Bi12b and Bi12c display significant agreement, but as these belong to two separate ships, two averages are made, one for each of Bi12b and Bi12c. The Bi12c average (Z157M004) is 178 years in length while the Bi12b average (Z157M005) is 162 years long.

The correlation between the average for Bi12a is shown in table 2. Very high agreement, expressed as t -values, is achieved with a range of regional and site chronologies that derive from West Swedish oak.

The correlations between the averages for Bi12b and Bi12c and diverse Northern European tree-ring datasets is shown in table 3. These two are achieving high t -values with material from shipwrecks in Oslo that derives from South Norwegian oak.

Method

When estimating the felling date for the trees used to make the planks from Bi12b and Bi12c a sapwood statistic for Norway (ca. 15 sapwood years (-8+6) (Christensen & Havemann 1998)) is used. For Bi12a a sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used. Several calculations of the average sapwood in oaks in different regions in Northern Europe have been published, and as the provenance of the oak trees for this ship tends towards southwest Sweden, I have here chosen to use a combination of the estimate for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) and for Southern Norway.

For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t -value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Bispevika 12a											
Z157001a x192	Bispevika 12a ship Oslo B3B7 2014096 X192 p286 køl del A QUSP	175	AD1365	AD1539	C	0	N	O	H1	1.09	after AD1550
Z157101a x175	Bispevika 12a ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x175 p403 QUSP	132	AD1412	AD1543	G	H/S	N	T	S1	1.99	AD1553-68
Z157102a x213	Bispevika 12a ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x213 p405 QUSP	116	AD1452	AD1567	G	15	N	T	S1	2.08	AD1568-77
Z157103a x186	Bispevika 12a ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x186 p404 QUSP	106	AD1441	AD1546	G	0	N	T	H1	2.07	AD1568-77
Z157104a x157	Bispevika 12a ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x157 p407 QUSP	158	AD1405	AD1562	G	11	N	T	S1	1.30	AD1563-76
Bispevika 12b											
Z157004a x048	Bispevika 12b ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x048 Hudbord p364 QUSP	142	AD1404	AD1545	V	0	N	T	H1	1.09	after AD1553
Z1570059 x063	Bispevika 12b ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x063 plank p365 QUSP	65	AD1501	AD1565	F	15	N	T	S1	1.50	AD1566-71
Bispevika 12c											
Z157002a x024	Bispevika 12c ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x024 Hudbord p362 QUSP	176	AD1382	AD1557	V	0	N	T	H1	0.89	after AD1565
Z1570039 x032	Bispevika 12c ship Oslo B3B7 03010143 x032 Hudbord p363 QUSP	146	AD1414	AD1559	V	10	N	T	S1	0.90	AD1560-70
same tree											
Z157102 103 st	Bispevika 12a ship Oslo same tree 1 QUSP	127	AD1441	AD1567	G	15	N	T	S1	2.07	AD1568-77
averages											
Z157M003	Bispevika ship 12a Oslo 4 timbers QUSP	203	AD1365	AD1567						1.58	
Z157M004	Bispevika ship 12c Oslo 2 timbers QUSP	178	AD1382	AD1559						0.88	
Z157M005	Bispevika ship 12b Oslo 2 timbers QUSP	162	AD1404	AD1565						1.21	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly PhD..			14 th November 2020								

When quoting these results please add the following:

in publication	Daly, A., 2020. Dendrochronological analysis of additional timbers from the ships Bispevika 12, Oslo. <i>dendro.dk report</i> 2020:46, Copenhagen.
bibliography/literature lists:	Oslo. <i>dendro.dk report</i> 2020:46, Copenhagen.
In blogs and social media:	<i>dendro.dk report</i> 2020:46